

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF RELAY PROTECTION OF THE ELECTRICITY SUPPLY OF A MINING AND PROCESSING PLANT

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Abstract

The paper presents the results of constructing an efficient relay protection in the power supply system of a mining and processing plant (MPP). A brief description of the MPP is given, as well as the corresponding power supply and equivalent circuits used to calculate short-circuit currents. A statistical analysis of damage in the MPP electrical network is performed, allowing conclusions to be drawn about the nature of damage distribution over the specified period. The analysis of the recorded damages shows that a significant portion of damages are single-phase ground faults, which in most cases turn into multi-phase short circuits disconnected by overcurrent protection (OCP). In order to improve the efficiency and reliability of the relay protection, the MPP power supply circuit is refined and analyzed. Using the refined power supply circuit, short-circuit currents are calculated, which in turn, having numerical values of short-circuit currents, allows calculating the relay protection settings and giving recommendations on the location of its installation and adjustment in order to ensure normal operation of electricity consumers. In order to reduce the number of cable insert damages on the line going to the administrative and amenity building (ABK) and to increase the reliability of power supply to consumers, it is advisable to divide the capacities of the existing 10 kV line into two parallel ones by laying a second line. It is recommended to install a current cutoff on the line going to the ABK, the feasibility of which has been shown by calculations. This will reduce the likelihood of cable insert damage. Data on the overcurrent protection and current cutoff settings are shown on the selectivity map. The presented research results are important for the implementation of educational programs such as EduNet (Phoenix Contact), PowerChute Network Shutdown (PCNS) and Network Management Card (NMC) (Schneider Electric), SITRAIN (Sie-mens), GIS K-MINE® ("KAI Scientific and Industrial Enterprise" LLC, Ukraine), VENTSIM and others for the training of mining engineers, especially for distance learning during a pandemic such as COVID-19 and other restrictions. The authors consider it appropriate to continue advanced research into high earth fault currents, as well as to develop recommendations for improving the operation of electrical networks, more complete use of existing networks, and ensuring safe service conditions at a mining and processing plant with a large number of mobile 6 kV transformer substations.

Keywords: mining and processing plant, power supply system, damage, relay protection, short-circuit currents, set-tings

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Statement of the problem

Further progress in improving the efficiency of enterprises is possible only with the correct use of scientific and technical solutions for the operation and optimal modes of operation of the power supply system (PSS). The correct choice of relay protection devices and their adjustment, leading to an increase in the selectivity and reliability of its operation, are of great importance for the optimal operation of the PSS. When the load of consumers changes, the operating mode of the PSS becomes different. Therefore, it is necessary to assess the effect of the load on losses in the PSS [1, 2].

Research object. The power supply system of the mining and processing plant (MPP), its brief characteristics, the corresponding power supply and equivalent circuits, as well as relay protection used to calculate short-circuit currents (SC).

The purpose of the research is to increase the efficiency of relay protection of the power supply of the mining and processing plant. This will increase the reliability and efficiency of the PSS of the mining and processing plants and achieve an economic effect.

To achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve the following problems.

Fig. 2. Number of damages on the feeder at the administrative and building complex for individual months of the year.

The cell 3 feeder to the tailings facility (see Fig. 3) illustrates the number of damages by time of year, with the majority occurring in February, April, May 2017, June 2018 and August 2019. A large number of damages registered in the specified months is determined, first of all, by insufficient pre-ventive measures carried out during this period and, secondly, by the small amount of precipitation that fell during this time. The causes of damage to electrical installations depend on many factors and are of a diverse nature. However, in almost all cases, the cause of damage and disconnection

of a particular element is not clear from the electrical equipment downtime log. Only which protection disconnects the damage is indicated. Damage can be divided into the following types: cable break-down, damage to overhead line insulators, breakage of overhead power lines, mechanical damage, damage to the supply line (short circuit on the line due to wire entanglement). Based on the types of damage, it would be advisable to make an entry in the electrical equipment downtime log about its cause after determining the type of damage [10, 11].

Fig. 3. Number of damages on the feeder of cell 3 at the tailings facility for individual months of the year

2.3. Analysis of damages in the electrical network of the mining and processing plant

To reduce the absolute number of damages in the 10 kV electrical network, the overall level of its operation should be increased. Particular care should be taken in carrying out preventive measures before the onset of spring and in winter, when these months account for the maximum number of damages. Particular attention should be paid to carrying out preventive work in the middle and at the end of the week, since the bulk of damages occur during this period. Since it is impossible to assess the damages from the electrical equipment downtime registration log, it is advisable for the substation duty personnel to find out the reason for the protection to operate and note it in the damage registration and accounting log. This is necessary for targeted preventive work to reduce individual types of damages.

2.4. Calculation of relay protection in electrical networks of the mining and processing plant

In recent years, electricity consumption in industry has been growing, which entails an increase in the capacity of transformers and the length of power transmission lines. Mining enterprises, one example of which is a mining and processing plant, are no exception [12, 13]. The main step-down substation of the mining and processing plant supplies the main and auxiliary units. The main units include the open-pit mine and the processing plant [14]. Auxiliary, but very important electricity consumers are such units as an urban-type settlement, a workshop for special garages, a concrete mixing plant, a club, a health resort, as well as neighboring villages, which are supplied with power lines from the mining and processing plant. The most important indicators of the normal operation of these power receivers are their uninterrupted power supply

and reliability. This does not always meet the specified requirement, since the electrical network has a significant branching, and the relay protection and automation do not work clearly and reliably enough [15, 16]. The consequence is non-selective disconnection of many electrical consumers, undersupply of electricity, mainly to residents of villages and, thus, downtime of electrical equipment. This in turn leads to deterioration of technical and economic indicators of many divisions and causes irreparable moral harm to the well-being of the population and personnel servicing the main and auxiliary production. All this causes the need for rationalization, increasing the efficiency and reliability of relay protection and automation in the electrical networks of the mining and processing plant [17, 18]. In order to increase the efficiency and reliability of relay protection, the power supply scheme of the mining and processing plant was clarified and analyzed. Using the clarified power supply scheme, short-circuit currents were calculated, which in turn, having numerical values of short-circuit currents, made it possible to calculate the relay protection settings and give recommendations

on the location of its installation and adjustment in order to ensure normal operation of electricity consumers [19, 20].

3. METHODOLOGY FOR CALCULATING SHORT-CIRCUIT CURRENTS

To calculate short-circuit currents in the power supply system of the mining and processing plant with a voltage of over 1000 V, calculation schemes and corresponding equivalent circuits of lines extending from the cells of the KRUN-10 kV GPP, the 10 kV "Promploshchadka" substation and the TsRP are compiled. Equivalent circuit for the circuit shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 4. The calculation uses the approximate reduction method, in which the voltage at all stages of transformation is taken to be equal to the average U_{av} , kV.

3.1. Calculation of short-circuit currents

To calculate the short-circuit current behind the transformer, we need to know the short-circuit power. To determine the short-circuit power (S_k) behind the power transformer GPP, we use the formula:

$$S_k = S_{t.nom} \cdot \frac{100}{u_k}, \quad (1)$$

Fig. 4. Equivalent circuit indicating the active and inductive resistances of the line extending from cell 3, 15 to the ABK

where $S_{t.nom}$ – the nominal power of the transformer, kVA; u_k , % – short-circuit voltage as a percentage of the nominal voltage U_n .

At the substation, a three-winding power transformer of type TDTN-25/110 with $u_k = 10,5$ kV for the winding with a voltage of 10.5 kV is installed.

$$S_k = 25000 \cdot \frac{100}{10,5} = 238095 \text{ kVA}. \quad (2)$$

The short-circuit current on the 10.5 kV side of the transformer at point K_1 is given by:

$$I_{k1} = \frac{S_k}{\sqrt{3} \cdot U_{av2}}, \quad (3)$$

where U_{cp2} – is the assumed average voltage value behind the transformer on the 10 kV side.

$$I_{k1} = \frac{238095}{\sqrt{3} \cdot 11} = 12500 \text{ A}. \quad (4)$$

According to the specified and refined power supply scheme of the mining and processing plant, a calculation model is developed. It takes into account that, when calculating short-circuit currents, it is necessary to include the active resistance if the ratio $r/x > 1/3$.

3.2. Calculation of resistance of individual elements of the electrical network

The system impedance is determined based on the calculated value of the short-circuit current behind the transformer on the 10.5 kV voltage side:

$$z_c = x_c = \frac{U_{av}}{\sqrt{3} \cdot I_{s.k.}} \quad (5)$$

$$z_c = x_c = \frac{110}{\sqrt{3} \cdot 12500} = 0,508 \text{ Om.} \quad (6)$$

The active and inductive resistances (r and x) of the cable and overhead lines are determined from the following considerations:

a) The inductive resistance of the cable is calculated based on the fact that $x_0=0,08$ Om/km – which is the specific impedance per kilometer of the line, depending on the line type, conductor material, and the method of construction of the 10.5 kV transmission line.

The total inductive resistance of the line is determined by the expression:

$$x_l = x_0 \cdot l, \quad (7)$$

where l – length of the line section, km;

b) The active resistance of the line is determined by the expression:

$$r = \frac{1000 \cdot l}{\gamma \cdot s}, \quad (8)$$

where γ – is the specific conductivity of cable lines: $\gamma=32$ – for aluminum and steel-aluminum conductors;

s – is the cross-sectional area of the line, mm²;

c) The inductive resistance of overhead lines is calculated using the same formula (4) for cable lines. The specific impedance per kilometer is taken from reference data.

The calculation of three-phase and two-phase short-circuit currents is performed using the following formulas:

$$I_k^{(3)} = \frac{U_{av}}{\sqrt{3} \cdot z_{res}} \quad (9)$$

$$I_k^{(2)} = I_k^{(3)} \cdot \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} \quad (10)$$

where z_{res} – is the resulting impedance of the short-circuit path (from the power source to the short-circuit point):

$$z_{res} = \sqrt{(x_{res})^2 + (r_{res})^2} \quad (11)$$

where $x_{res} = \sum_{1}^n x = x_1 + x_2 + \dots + x_n$ – is

the sum of the inductive resistances of the line segments up to the short-circuit point;

$r_{res} = \sum_{1}^n r = r_1 + r_2 + \dots + r_n$ – is the sum of the active resistances of the line segments up to the short-circuit point.

Since the condition: $r/x > 1/3$, is met, the active resistance r_{res} must be taken into account when calculating the short-circuit currents. Using the formulas above, the values of the three-phase and two-phase short-circuit currents are calculated. The equivalent circuit, indicating the values of the network element resistances to be calculated, is shown in Fig. 4. The results of the three-phase and two-phase short-circuit current calculations for the line branching from cells 3 and 15 at the administration building (AB) are summarized in Table 1.

3.3. Drawing up a map of selectivity of operation of maximum current protection in the electrical network of the mining and processing plant

In accordance with the Electrical Installation Code, "on single lines with one-way power supply from multiphase short circuits, as a rule, a two-stage current protection must be installed, the first stage of which is implemented in the form of a current cutoff (CCP), and the second - in the form of an overcurrent protection (OCP) with an independent or dependent time delay characteristic.

Since the mixed cable-overhead network with a voltage of 10 kV of the mining and processing plant is an open radial network with one-way power supply, the installation and calculation of CCP and OCP are provided for it.

The selection map of the relay protection is compiled in the following sequence:

a) an equivalent circuit for the electrical network (for each of the lines considered above) is compiled;

b) the resistances of individual elements of the circuit are determined in accordance with the brand, cross-section and length of the lines;

c) the currents of three- and two-phase short circuits at individual points of the network are calculated;

d) the tripping currents of the protections are determined at the connection points of the step-down substations and on each outgoing line at the installation points of the protections;

e) the sensitivity coefficient k_{ch} is determined;

f) the overcurrent protection time delays are set.

Table 1. Data for calculating short-circuit currents and the magnitude of three- and two-phase short-circuit currents

Short circuit point	r_{res}, Om	x_{res}, Om	z_{res}, Om	$I_K^{(3)}, A$	$I_K^{(2)}, A$
K ₁	–	0,508	0,508	12501	10826
K ₂	0,018	0,5168	0,5171	12281	10635
K ₃	0,068	0,5232	0,5276	12037	10424
K ₄	0,256	0,5472	0,6041	10512	9103
K ₅	0,35	0,5612	0,6614	9602	8315
K ₆	0,734	0,6092	0,9538	6658	5765
K ₇	1,033	0,6612	1,2264	5178	4484
K ₈	0,9916	0,654	1,1878	5346	4630
K ₉	0,67	0,6012	0,9001	7055	6110
K ₁₀	0,697	0,6092	0,9257	6860	5941
K ₁₁	0,798	0,6172	1,0088	6295	5452
K ₁₂	0,986	0,6412	1,1761	5399	4676
K ₁₃	1,63	0,7212	1,7824	3563	3085
K ₁₄	1,6576	0,726	1,8096	3509	3039
K ₁₅	2,5776	0,886	2,7256	2330	–

Using the data on the calculation of three- and two-phase short-circuit currents for individual out-going radial lines, we calculate the tripping current and check the selected protections for sensitivity. The tripping current of the maximum current protection is determined by the formula:

$$I_{t.c} = \frac{k_r \cdot k_{ss}}{k_{ret}} \cdot I_{work.max}, \quad (12)$$

where $k_r=1,1-1,2$ – reliability coefficient;

k_{ss} – self-start coefficient;

$I_{work.max}$ – maximum operating current (nominal current of the consumers), A;

k_{ret} – reset coefficient: $k_{ret}=0,6-0,7$ – for RTM-type relays; $k_{ret}=0,8-0,85$ – for RS40-type relays.

The relay trip current is determined by the formula:

$$I_{t.c} = \frac{k_{sh} \cdot I_{s.z}}{n_{tt}}, \quad (13)$$

where $k_{sch.c}$ – is the scheme coefficient, equal to 1 when two relays are connected to phase currents in a partial star circuit, and equal to $\sqrt{3}$ when one relay is connected to the difference between the currents of two phases;

n_{ct} – is the current transformer ratio.

The sensitivity coefficient is determined by the expression:

$$k_s = \frac{I_{sc.min}}{I_{av} \cdot n_{TT}} = \frac{I_{s.c}^{(2)}}{I_{s.z}}, \quad (14)$$

where $I_{s.c}^{(2)}=I_{s.c.min}$ – is the two-phase short-circuit current at the end of the protected zone (section).

According to the PUE, the value of k_s should be: $k_s \geq 1,5$ – for short circuits at the end of the protected section; $k_s \geq 1,2$ – for short circuits at the end of the adjacent section when the time-current protection (MTZ) operates as backup protection, and for current cutoffs implemented as backup protection.

The calculation of the trip current for the current cutoff will be performed using the formula:

$$I_{t.c} = k_n \cdot I_{s.c.sn.max}^{(3)} \quad (15)$$

where $k_n=1,2-1,4$;

$I_{s.c.sn.max}^{(3)}$ – the three-phase short-circuit current at the beginning of the adjacent section, A.

4. GRAPHIC-ANALYTICAL CALCULATION OF RELAY PROTECTION OF OUTGOING LINES

Example 1. Input Data. The line is the output to the administrative building (ABK) from cells 3 and 15 (see Fig. 1); a) time-current protection (MTZ) is installed on OS₁ (near the "2nd lift" substation) on the considered line.

Solution. We calculate the maximum load $I_{work.max}$ based on the nominal power of the transformers connected to the outgoing line after OS₁ (see Fig. 1). We determine the trip current for OS₁ using the expression (8):

$$I_{t.c} = \frac{1,2 \cdot 2,5}{0,85} \cdot 46,7 = 164,8 \quad (16)$$

where

$$I_{work.max} = \frac{\sum_{n,t} S_{n,t}}{\sqrt{3} \cdot U_n} = \frac{850}{\sqrt{3} \cdot 10,5} = 46,7 \text{ A.}$$

The relay trip current is calculated using the expression (17):

$$I_{t.c} = \frac{1 \cdot 164,8}{10} = 16,4 \text{ A.} \quad (17)$$

For installation, we choose an electromagnetic microprocessor relay of the type RS40/20 with a trip current of 17 A. We check the protection sensitivity using expression (18):

$$k_s = \frac{2017}{17 \cdot 10} = 11,8. \quad (18)$$

$k_s > 1,5$, the protection is sufficiently sensitive to the short-circuit current at the start of the protection zone (at point K₁₅).

Operation of the 10 kV networks on the outgoing lines from RP-10 has shown that on the section of the outgoing line to the administrative building (ABK), when short-circuit currents of around 10–12 kA occur, which happens in the actual network, the cable insert at the beginning of the mentioned line frequently fails. This leads to a power outage for a large number of consumers, including a village that is supplied by this line [21, 22].

The primary reason for this is the large magnitude of the short-circuit current and the significant time delay of the relay protection acting to disconnect this current [23, 24]. To reduce the vulnerability of the cable insert and increase the reliability of power supply to consumers, it would be advisable to divide the specified line into two parallel lines. This will require, initially in agreement with the chief energy department, the separate utilization of cells 3 and 15 at the 10 kV

"Prompleshadka" substations, the installation of 11 poles, and the laying of 450 meters of A-50 wire.

Limiting the short-circuit current can be achieved by installing a reactor type РБ-10-630-0.25. This will enhance the reliability of the oil circuit breakers during short-circuit current disconnection (the calculated values of short-circuit resistance and short-circuit currents for the line departing from cells 3 and 15 at AB, considering the resistance of the linear reactor after the installation of the RB-10-630-0.25 reactor, are presented in Table 2).

From the data in Table 2, it follows that the installation of the reactor will significantly reduce short-circuit currents and improve the reliability of the GOK's power supply system. Therefore, it seems reasonable to submit a request for the preparation of this reactor. However, due to the current inability to install the reactor, it is proposed to increase the response speed of the existing overcurrent protection, which has a time delay. For this purpose, it is recommended to install a current cutoff on the feeder leading to the ABK, the calculation of which is provided below. [25].

Table 2. Active and inductive resistances for calculating short-circuit currents and determined values of three- and two-phase short-circuit currents

Short circuit point	r_{res}, Om	x_{res}, Om	z_{res}, Om	$I_k^{(3)}, \text{A}$	$I_k^{(2)}, \text{A}$
K ₁	–	0,758	0,758	8378	7255
K ₂	0,0180	0,7704	0,7706	8241	7137
K ₃	0,068	0,7768	0,7797	8145	7053
K ₄	0,256	0,8008	0,844	7524	6516
K ₅	0,35	0,8148	0,8867	7162	6202
K ₆	0,734	0,8628	1,1327	5606	4856
K ₇	1,033	0,9148	1,3798	4602	3986
K ₈	0,9916	0,9076	1,3442	4724	4091
K ₉	0,67	0,8548	1,086	5847	5064
K ₁₀	0,697	0,8628	1,1091	5726	4959
K ₁₁	0,798	0,8708	1,1811	5377	4657
K ₁₂	0,986	0,8948	1,3314	4770	4130
K ₁₃	1,6576	0,9448	1,8992	3343	2896
K ₁₄	1,6576	0,94	1,9055	3333	2886
K ₁₅	2,5776	1,1	2,8025	2266	1963

Let's determine the sensitivity coefficient for the overcurrent protection on the oil circuit breaker MV1 after the possible installation of the reactor (taking into account the calculated short-circuit currents in Table 3) using expression (10):

$$k_s = \frac{1963}{10 \cdot 17} = 11,5 \quad (19)$$

It is evident that after the installation of the reactor, the protection sensitivity remains very high. Therefore, it will function quite effectively.

Example 2. Initial data. For the calculation of the overcurrent protection on the oil circuit breaker MVCRP at the beginning of the outgoing line to the ABK (cell 3 or 15).

Solution. Similarly to the previous calculation, we assume that the maximum operating current corresponds to the current: $I_n = I_{p,max} = 300 \text{ A}$.

We determine the activation current of the overcurrent protection using expression (20):

$$I_{t.c} = \frac{1,2 \cdot 2,5}{0,85} \cdot 300 = 1058 \text{ A.} \quad (20)$$

The relay activation current will be equal to the formula (21):

$$I_{a.c.r} = \frac{1 \cdot 1058}{60} = 17,6 \text{ A.} \quad (21)$$

The selected relay is of the type RS40/20 with a current rating of 20 A and $I_{a.c.r} = 18 \text{ A}$.

We determine the sensitivity coefficient before the installation of the reactor using expression (14):

$$k_s = \frac{3085}{18 \cdot 60} = 2,86. \quad (22)$$

After the installation of the reactor:

$$k_s = \frac{2896}{18 \cdot 60} = 2,68. \quad (23)$$

Thus, the maximum current protection will be sensitive both before and after the installation of the reactor.

Example 3. Initial data. For the calculation of the activation current of the current cutoff on the line outgoing to the ABK from cell 3 or 15 for the OS_{CDS}.

Solution. The calculation is carried out using formula (15):

- Before the installation of the reactor:

$$I_{t.c} = k_n \cdot I_{s.c.(k13)max}^{(3)} = 1,3 \cdot 3563 = 4631,9 \text{ A};$$

$$I_{t.co} = \frac{I_{t.c.to}}{n_{tt}} = \frac{4631,9}{60} = 77,2 \text{ A. (24)}$$

The selected relay is of the type RS40/100 with $I_{t.c}=80 \text{ A}$. The sensitivity coefficient is determined using expression (10):

$$k_s = \frac{I_{s.c.(k1)}^{(2)}}{I_{t.c} \cdot n_{tt}} = \frac{10826}{80 \cdot 60} = 2,26. (25)$$

The current cutoff is sensitive since $k_s > 2$.

- After the installation of the reactor:

$$I_{t.c.t} = k_n \cdot I_{s.c.(k13)max}^{(3)} = 1,3 \cdot 3343 = 4345,9 \text{ A};$$

$$I_{t.c.T.} = \frac{I_{s.c.to}}{n_{tt}} = \frac{4345,9}{60} = 72,43 \text{ A. (26)}$$

$l_{work}^{(2)}$ – working area for two-phase short circuit (73,8% l_{gen});
 $l_{work}^{(3)}$ – working area for three-phase short circuit (81,2% l_{gen}).

The selected relay is of the type RS40/100 with $I_{t.c}=75 \text{ A}$. The sensitivity coefficient is determined using expression (10):

$$k_s = \frac{I_{s.c.(k1)}^{(2)}}{I_{t.c} \cdot n_{tt}} = \frac{7255}{75 \cdot 60} = 1,7. (27)$$

5. CURRENT CUTOFF EFFICIENCY

The efficiency of the current cutoff after the reactor installation decreased to $k_{ch}=1.7$. However, in accordance with the Electrical Installation Code, “for current cutoffs without time delay installed on lines and performing additional protection functions, the sensitivity coefficient should be about 1.2 during a short circuit at the protection installation location in the most favorable mode according to the sensitivity condition [26, 27].

The efficiency of the current cutoff for the line under consideration is determined graphically for two modes (Fig. 5):

- before the reactor installation (Fig. 5, a);
- after the reactor installation (Fig. 5, b).

From Fig. 5 it is evident that the minimum value of the current cutoff operating zone is 54% of the entire line length, i.e. the cutoff is effective in both cases (with and without the reactor).

$l_{work}^{(2)}$ – working area for two-phase short circuit ($54,4\% \cdot l_{gen}$);
 $l_{work}^{(3)}$ – working area for three-phase short circuit ($65,8\% \cdot l_{gen}$);
 l_{dz} – dead zone of current cutoff

Fig. 5. Graphic definition of the current cutoff working zone

The response time of the protection on the line under consideration is shown in Fig. 1 and in Table. 3 construction of a selectivity map, where the protection settings are indicated for the primary and secondary currents $I_{c,r}$ and $I_{t,c}$ [28, 29].

Similar calculations were performed for all other substations of the mining and processing plant using the given methodology, the results of which are presented in the conclusions. In our opinion, the following new scientific and methodological provisions deserve attention:

Table 3. Map of selectivity of relay protection when powering electrical consumers from radial lines with a voltage of 10 kV

The name of the outgoing line	Place of installation of protection	Type of protection	Type of current relay	k_{sh}	$I_{t.c.}, A$	n_{tt}	$I_{t.c.}, A$	k_s	t, s	Note
This is cell 3, 15 on AB	OS ₁	MTZ	PT-40/20	1	170	50/5	17	11,8	0	
	OS _{CDS}	MTZ	PT-40/20	1	1080	300/5	18	2,8	0,6	
		TO	PT-40/100	1	4800	300/5	80	2,26	0	to the installation of the reactor
			4500	75	1,7		after installing the reactor			
From cell 14, output №2 to CMM	OS ₂	MTZ	PT-40/50	1	520	100/5	26	6,5	0	$I_{work,max}=146,2 A$
	OS _{ZMM}	MTZ	PT-40/50	1	760	100/5	38	13,7	0,6	$I_{work,max}=215,5 A$
From cell №4 output №1 to ZZB	OS ₂	MTZ	PT-40/50	1	520	100/5	26	6,5	0	$I_{work,max}=146,2 A$
	OS _{ZZB}	MTZ	PT-40/20	1	900	300/5	15	5,6	0,6	
		TO	PT-40/100	1	6000	300/5	100	1,78	0	
From cell №15, input to TS-9	OS ₂	MTZ	PTM	1	480	150/5	16	3,6	0	
	OS ₁	MTZ	PTB	1	750	150/5	25	2,9	0,6	
	OS _{CDS}	MTZ	PT-40/20	1	1020	300/5	17	7,8	1,1	
Output from the 3rd cell of KRUN 10 kV	OS _{KRUN}	MTZ	PT-40/50	1	720	150/5	24	3,5	0	$I_{p,max}=218,8 A$

The operational reliability of the power supply of developing ore mining and enrichment sites is assessed to ensure greater flexibility of the power supply system for mining operations, as well as to improve the reliability and safety of electrical installations in networks

of various voltages when expanding the front of mining operations both by underground and open-pit methods.

The parameters of power consumption for individual process and auxiliary sections of the quarry (overburden, copper ore mining, loading from quartzite

dumps, loading from barite ore dumps, basalt stone mining, basalt stone crushing) are determined.

A method for predicting specific power consumption for individual process sections of the quarry using modern software has been developed. To improve the selectivity of relay protection, three- and two-phase short-circuit currents in 6 kV quarry networks have been calculated, and experimental studies of single-phase short circuits in the quarry and enrichment plant networks have been presented.

Recommendations are given on the values of relay protection settings against short circuits and the use of directional protection against single-phase earth faults. In general, the proposed recommendations allow for current monitoring of electricity consumption and for achieving an economic effect by improving the operation of relay protection.

The presented research results are of great importance in the implementation of educational programs such as EduNet (Phoenix Contact), PowerChute Network Shutdown (PCNS) and Network Management Card (NMC) (Schneider Electric), SITRAIN (Siemens) [30, 31], GIS K-MINE® ("KAI Scientific and Industrial Enterprise" LLC, Ukraine) [32], VENTSIM and others for the training of mining engineers in universities and advanced training institutes, especially for distance learning during a pandemic such as COVID-19 and other restrictions [33]. As the analysis shows, industrial enterprises of Kryvbas (ArcelorMittal Kryvyi Rih, GOK MetinvestHolding, Heidelberg Cement, etc.) have already accumulated significant experience in the successful application of similar approaches based on the technologies of world leaders Phoenix Contact, Schneider Electric, Siemens, etc. [34, 35].

6. CONCLUSION

1. In order to reduce the number of cable insert damages on the line going to the administrative and amenity building and to increase the reliability of power supply to consumers, it is advisable to divide the capacities of the existing 10 kV line into two parallel lines by laying a second line. This will require separately using cells 3 and 15, installing 11 supports and laying 450 m of A-50 cross-section wires.

2. The short-circuit current can be limited by installing a reactor of the RB-10-630-0.25 type. This will increase the reliability of the oil circuit breakers when disconnecting short-circuit currents (calculated values of short-circuit circuit resistances and short-circuit currents before and after installing a reactor of the RB-10-630-0.25 type (see Table 1 and Table 2).

3. It is recommended to install a current cutoff on the line going to the administrative and amenity building, the feasibility of which has been shown by calculations. This will reduce the likelihood of damage to the cable insert. Data on the setting currents of the overcurrent protection and overcurrent protection are given on the selectivity map (Table 3).

4. It is recommended to set the minimum operating time of the relay protection on the outgoing lines. On the outgoing line from cell 14, terminal No. 2 to the CMM, at the installation site of the MV2, install 150/5 current transformers with $I_n = 150$ A instead of the existing 100/5, since $I_{p.max} = 146.2$ A. At the installation

site of the MVCMM, it is necessary to replace the existing current transformers with $n_{tt}=100/5$ on CT with $n_{tt}=250/5$, since $I_{p.max}=215.5$ A. On the outgoing line "output from the 3rd cell of the KRUN-10 kV" it is necessary to install a current transformer with $n_{tt}=250/5$ instead of the existing current transformers with $n_{tt}=150/5$, since $I_{p.max}=218.8$ A.

5. The authors consider it appropriate to continue prospective studies of large earth fault currents, as well as the development of recommendations for improving the operation of electrical networks. As well as more complete use of existing network-works and ensuring safe conditions for their maintenance at the mining and processing plant with a large number of mobile transformer substations with a voltage of 6 kV.

6. It was proposed to use the technologies of the world's leading industrial automation companies (Phoenix Contact, Schneider Electric, Siemens) for the implementation of promising projects, based on many years of successful experience of their application at the leading mining and metallurgical enterprises of Kryvbas (including ArcelorMittal Kryvyi Rih, MetinvestHolding Mining and Processing Plants, Heidelberg Cement, etc.).

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